

creased grain yield compared to the no-nitrogen check. Response to nitrogen applied under various treatments ranged from 6 to 40 kg grain/kg N (see table). highest grain yield was recorded when urea supergranules were deep-placed in the root zone. Neem cake and lac-coated urea produced equal grain yields that were lower than those with supergranules. When nitrogen was applied as equal splits of urea at planting and panicle initiation, grain yield was much lower than that in the other treatments. Farmyard manure-coated urea did not perform well. Urea applied at planting produced lowest grain yields.

The experiment showed the benefits of applying nitrogen to lowland rice and the effectiveness of urea supergranule deep placement. □

Grain yield, nitrogen response, and some agronomic characters as influenced by different nitrogen treatments in transplanted rice under rainfed lowland conditions, Malan, India.

N source	Time and rate (kg/ha) of N application			Efficiency of nitrogen (kg grain/kg N)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Panicle weight (g)
	Planting	Panicle initiation	Total				
Control	0	0	0	—	1.1	210	1.93
Urea	60	0	60	6	1.4	261	1.95
Urea	30	30	60	24	2.5	289	2.13
Urea (neem cake coated)	60	0	60	33	3.1	405	2.14
Urea (farmyard manure coated)	60	0	60	23	2.5	245	1.98
Urea supergranule	60	0	60	40	3.5	429	2.12
Granulated compost	60	0	60	22	2.4	241	1.96
Urea (lac-coated)	60	0	60	33	3.1	423	2.11
CD 5%					0.1	27	0.09

Cropping systems

Fertilizer nitrogen management in wheat - summer mung - rice crop rotation

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Rice - wheat is the most common crop rotation followed by farmers in the Punjab because it produces high yields. As the rice - wheat area has increased, pulse production has declined. Pulse production can be increased by planting a wheat - summer mung - rice rotation using G-65 mung, which matures in 60 days.

We studied a wheat - summer mung - rice rotation in 1979-80 rabi with the objective of increasing pulse production and using mung straw as green manure to provide nitrogen to rice.

The crops were grown at the PAU farm in loamy sand soil, with pH 8.2 and 0.17% O.C. Immediately after wheat was harvested in mid-Apr, the field was irrigated and mung G-65 at 20 kg/ha was sown between the wheat rows. The mung crop depended on residual fertility after the wheat crop, which received 120 kg N, 26 kg P, and 25 kg K/ha. The mung crop matured the 4th week of Jun, which

Grain and straw yield of mung and mung straw nitrogen content, Ludhiana, India.

Item	1980	1981	1982	Mean
Grain yield of mung (t/ha)	0.84	0.85	0.89	0.86
Fresh weight of mung straw (t/ha)	7.6	7.6	7.5	7.6
Dry weight of mung straw (t/ha)	4.6	4.6	4.5	4.6
N content of mung straw (%)	2.16	2.21	2.26	2.21
N added through straw (kg/ha)	99.4	101.7	101.7	100.9

coincided with the beginning of the monsoon when farmers generally do not have enough covered space to keep the produce before it is dried and threshed. The pods were manually picked and mung straw was incorporated 1 day before rice was transplanted.

Average mung yield was 0.86 t/ha. Mung straw weighed 7.6 t fresh weight/ha and 4.6 t dry weight/ha, which added 101 kg N/ha to the soil (see table).

The figure shows that green manuring with mung straw 1 day before rice transplanting produced higher rice yields than using 60 kg N/ha where mung straw was removed. Mung straw and 60 kg N/ha

produced rice yields equal to those with 120 kg N/ha in treatments where mung straw was removed. □

Effect of summer mung straw green manure on rice yield, 1980-82.